

ART STUDIES

THE DEBATE ON WRITING THE NATIONAL DISCOURSE OF CHINESE MUSIC ART CRITICISM IN THE POST-NEW PERIOD

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Abstract

In the field of Chinese music art criticism in the post-new period, there has always been a debate about national discourse. The core issue of this debate involves how to define and express the nationality in Chinese music art, and under this background, what kind of ghostwriting and interpretation can best convey this nationality. In the ongoing development and modernization of Chinese music art, music critics and critics have been exploring how to incorporate elements of traditional Chinese music into contemporary music creation, and how to cope with the cultural shock of globalization to ensure the local and traditional nature of Chinese music. This paper aims to analyze the debates on ghostwriting in the field of Chinese music art in the post-New era, with a special focus on the various definitions and practices of national discourse, and the key issues behind these debates.

Key words: Post-new period, Chinese music art, national discourse, ghostwriting debate, retroism.

Introduction:

In the post-new period, the field of Chinese music art criticism has always been full of fierce debates, especially the controversy of ghostwriting about national discourse. During this period, China's music culture has undergone profound changes, from traditional music to modern music. The wave of globalization and technological progress has made the expression of music more diversified. Against this backdrop, how to convey China's cultural identity and national characteristics in music has become a hotly debated topic. The core issue of this generation's writing debate involves how to define and express nationality in Chinese musical art, and what kind of ghostwriting and interpretation can best convey this nationality in this context.

1. The evolution of Chinese music art in the post-New era

The evolution of Chinese music art in the post-New period is a complex and diversified process, which reflects the great changes in China's social, cultural and technological environment. In the post-new period, Chinese music art has undergone a profound evolution, reflecting multifaceted changes in society, culture and technology. This period, roughly from the late 1980s to the early 21st century, marked a new stage of modernization and globalization for Chinese music. Post-new period Chinese music was greatly influenced by globalization, and musicians and creators began to communicate with international musical styles and genres. This has led to the mixing and fusion of musical elements to create new musical forms, while also expanding the international influence of Chinese music. The rapid development of technology has provided unprecedented opportunities for music production and distribution. The proliferation of digital recording and the Internet has changed the way music is made and distributed, allowing more musicians and creators to enter the music scene and interact^[1] with audiences. During this period, discussions on the national discourse of Chinese music became particularly important. The music field began to explore how to preserve and promote China's traditional musical elements in modern music so as to

maintain the uniqueness of Chinese music. In the post-new period, many different genres of music have emerged in Chinese music, including pop, rock, folk, electronic music and jazz. These genres reflect the aesthetic orientations of different musicians and listeners, making Chinese music more diversified. Music education and the music industry in China have also experienced significant development. The popularity of music academies and music disciplines has trained generations of musicians, while the growth of the music industry has provided more opportunities for music creators. The evolution of Chinese music art in the post-new period reflects the modernization and globalization trend of Chinese society, and at the same time highlights the pluralism of China's music field. The debate of national discourse plays an important role in this process, reflecting the challenges of Chinese music in how to express its uniqueness and cope with cultural globalization. The musical evolution of this period brought new opportunities and challenges to Chinese music, and at the same time contributed to the diversification of the world music field.

Second, the importance of national discourse

National discourse helps maintain and promote the cultural identity of Chinese music. China has a rich musical tradition, including traditional folk music, opera and classical music. By preserving and passing on these traditional elements, music can convey the uniqueness of Chinese culture and help build the international image of Chinese music. National discourse helps pass on traditional Chinese musical elements to a new generation of musicians and listeners. This inheritance includes not only the techniques and expressions of the music, but also the cultural background, values and historical memory. Through music, the traditions of Chinese culture can be revitalized and passed on to the next generation. The discussion of national discourse has prompted music creators to explore how to preserve traditional elements in music while achieving innovation. This balance is crucial to the development of music, which enables it to make connections between tradition and modernity, creating works that are both unique and

have modern appeal. The ghostwriting of national discursive can help boost the cultural confidence of Chinese music. This can prompt musicians and creators to be more confident in bringing Chinese music to the international stage, while also sending a message of cultural confidence at home. National discourses help maintain cultural diversity. China is home to numerous ethnic minorities, each with their own unique musical traditions. By encouraging ghostwriting of ethnic discourses, the musical heritage of each ethnic group can be preserved and promoted, and cultural diversity promoted. National discourses help shape the cultural identity of individuals and societies. Music is one of the expressions of cultural identity, which can build resonance and cohesion in society and make people more proud to identify with their own culture^[2]. The importance of national discourse in Chinese music art in the post-new era is reflected in the aspects of maintaining cultural inheritance, promoting cultural diversity, shaping cultural identity and improving cultural self-confidence. This discourse helps Chinese music to find a balance in the era of globalization and realize the integration of tradition and modernity. At the same time, it helps Chinese music to stand out on the international stage and become a unique form of music.

3. The historical background of the Ghostwriting debate

During the Cultural Revolution, music in China was subject to severe political interference and censorship, and traditional music and cultural elements were criticized and suppressed. This period had a profound impact on the way music was created and expressed in China, and the art of music hit a low point. China's reform and opening up policy has brought new opportunities to the music sector. Musicians and creators began exploring different musical styles and forms, absorbing international musical elements, reactivating traditional musical elements, and seeking diversity in music. In the late 1980s and early 1990s, China's music scene began to be affected by the wave of globalization. The entry of international music genres and cultures into China has made music more diversified. This has led to discussions on how to preserve the national character in Chinese music. During the reform and opening up period, China's traditional music has also experienced a certain revival. Traditional musical elements such as folk music, opera and classical music have received renewed attention, and music colleges have begun to train traditional music teachers, contributing to the protection and development of traditional music. The rapid development of the Internet and digital technology has changed the way music is made and disseminated. Music production has become easier, music can be distributed more widely, and musicians and creators can collaborate more easily across cultures. With the development of diversified and globalized music in China, discussions on national discourses have been on the rise. Music critics, musicians and cultural scholars began to explore how to ghostwrite and express Chinese

cultural identity and traditional elements in music. The debate between music critics and creators has become more heated. Some advocate ghostwriting national character through conservative and traditional means, while others favor innovation and fusion. The debate raises key questions about the future direction of Chinese music. The historical context of the ghostwriting debate reflects the political, social and cultural changes in the art of music in China, as well as the different views and orientations^[3] of the music industry in the face of these changes. This background provides a key explanation for the complexity and pluralism of the ghostwriting debates in China in the post-new era.

Fourth, the different methods of ghostwriting nationality

Retro and traditionalism This approach emphasizes the conservative inheritance of traditional Chinese musical elements. Music creators use classical instruments, traditional tones and musical forms to perform and create music in a traditional way. The goal of this method is to faithfully inherit and preserve the traditional elements of Chinese music to maintain its purity. **The hybridism approach** combines traditional Chinese elements with international musical styles to create fusion music. This may include blending with Western pop, rock, electronic music and other styles to create a unique sound. This approach promotes cross-cultural exchange of music and makes Chinese music more modern. **The innovationist approach** emphasizes the forward-looking and original nature of music. Musicians express China's national character through innovative musical elements, new playing techniques and sound experiments. This approach often involves the reinterpretation and reimagining of traditional musical elements to create a unique musical experience. **Folk music** is used as a method to introduce Chinese folk music elements into music creation. This may include using traditional folk instruments, adopting the rhythms and melodies of rural music, and telling folk stories and traditional subject matter. This approach emphasizes the presentation^[4] of rural Chinese culture and lifestyle. Some musicians combine elements of traditional Chinese music with ceremonial music, such as religious music or celebration music. This method conveys the sense of ritual and solemnity of Chinese culture through the ceremonial performance of music. Some musicians use sound experiments and electronic music techniques to re-enact traditional Chinese musical elements. They may use synthesizers, digital sound effects and sound processing to create modern music while preserving the Chinese national character. These different approaches represent a diverse exploration of the national character of Chinese music ghostwriting. Musicians and creators can choose different methods according to their aesthetic views, creative goals and musical styles to express Chinese cultural characteristics in music. The use of these methods also reflects the diverse views of the music industry on how to deal with the challenges of a globalized culture.

Chinese folk music refers to the traditional folk music performed by Chinese traditional instruments in the form of solo or ensemble.

Chinese folk music is generally divided into five categories, namely songs, singing and dancing music, rap music, opera music and instrumental music.

Fifth, write the key issues of the debate

1. Defining the nationality of Chinese music

The nationality of Chinese music means that the music contains the characteristics of Chinese culture, history and tradition, and reflects the elements of Chinese national identity and cultural identity. These characteristics may include the musical elements of traditional Chinese music, such as traditional tones, instruments and musical forms, as well as the cultural themes and values conveyed in the music. Nationality can also be expressed in the way the music is played, lyrics and themes of the song. The nationality of Chinese music is also a cultural expression, reflecting the cultural identity and historical inheritance of the Chinese people. This definition emphasizes the role of Chinese music as a cultural expression, which includes not only musical forms and elements, but also cultural context and emotional transmission. However, it is important to note that different people may have different understandings of the national character of Chinese music, which is also a key aspect of the ghostwriting debate. Whether the nationality of ghostwriting music should include traditional musical elements, regional characteristics, cultural symbols, etc., may spark debate and discussion^[5].

(2) Balance between conservatism and innovation

The view of traditional conservatism holds that when ghostwriting the national character of Chinese music, emphasis should be placed on retaining traditional musical elements and techniques. This approach emphasizes faithfully inheriting the traditions of Chinese music, including the use of traditional instruments, tones and musical forms. Traditional conservatism advocates keeping the original flavor of Chinese music to preserve its uniqueness and cultural inheritance. The innovationist view holds that ghostwriting the national

character of Chinese music needs to adapt to changes in modern society through innovation. This approach emphasizes creative reinterpretation of traditional elements while introducing new musical elements and techniques. Innovationism advocates incorporating elements of globalization and modernization into music in order to make Chinese music more attractive. Some views advocate blending traditional and innovative elements in music to achieve balance. This approach holds that tradition and innovation are not mutually exclusive, but can complement each other. Music creators can retain traditional musical elements while introducing innovative ways of expression to create unique music. Balancing tradition and innovation also requires consideration of audience needs and market trends. Sometimes, music creators may need to balance tradition and innovation based on audience tastes and market trends to meet audience needs. Music education plays an important role in balancing tradition and innovation. While music education can develop musicians' skills, it should also encourage students to be innovative and experiment. In addition, music education can impart knowledge and skills of traditional music to help preserve and pass on traditional music. The balance between conservatism and innovation is a complex and challenging task when ghostwriting the national character of Chinese music. Different musicians and creators may take different approaches, depending on their aesthetic views, musical styles and creative goals. The realization of this balance needs to take into account both the preservation of traditional music and the creation of innovative music to ensure that Chinese music both retains its unique cultural characteristics and can appeal to modern audiences.

(3) Cultural impact of globalization

Globalization has led to the mutual exchange and integration of Chinese music with other musical cultures around the world. This enriches the diversity of Chinese music, but also brings challenges^[6] to the management of cultural diversity. Musicians need to adapt to different cultural influences while preserving their national identity. Some people worry that globalization has led to the invasion of Chinese music by Western music culture. They believe that the traditional elements and values of Chinese music may be impacted by Western music culture, thus losing its uniqueness. Globalization has also provided musicians with opportunities to communicate and cooperate with the international music community. Such exchanges can stimulate musicians' creativity and inspire them to blend different cultural elements to create new musical forms. Globalization has made it easier for Chinese music to enter the international market. Chinese musicians can take their music globally and attract international audiences through the Internet and digital technology. This brings more market opportunities for Chinese musicians. The globalization culture shock has also led to discussions on cultural self-confidence and cultural protection. Some people advocate showing Chinese cultural confidence through music, while the protection of traditional music should also be strengthened to cope with the cultural shock brought about by globalization. Globalization has promoted cross-cultural cooperation, and musicians can co-create and perform with international musicians. This helps Chinese music integrate global cultural elements, while also providing international audiences with more opportunities to learn about Chinese music. The cultural shock of globalization has brought both opportunities and challenges in the national character of ghostwriting Chinese music. Musicians need to carefully balance traditional and modern,

local and global elements to ensure that Chinese music is both national and stands out on the international stage. It also requires strengthening cultural self-confidence, while also paying attention to cultural protection to cope with the cultural shock of globalization.

(4) Cultural identity and cultural conflict

The national character of Chinese music writing can strengthen the Chinese people's sense of identity of their own culture. Through music, people can express their pride in Chinese culture and pass it on to the next^[7] generation. This helps consolidate the Chinese cultural identity. Ghostwriting the national character of Chinese music can also broaden the scope of Chinese cultural identity. Music can show the diversity of different regions, ethnic minorities and historical periods in China, giving people a better understanding of the complexity of Chinese culture. With increasing globalization, Chinese music is facing the challenge of cultural conflicts on the international stage. The values and aesthetic views of different cultures can lead to conflicts, and music creators need to deal with these challenges. Ghostwriting the nationality of Chinese music can promote cultural integration. Chinese music can absorb elements from other cultures and influence international music at the same time. This mutual influence can promote cultural exchange and understanding. Music can also reflect the diversity of cultural identities. Different music genres and styles can represent the identity of different cultural groups, thus enriching the diversity of Chinese cultural identity. Some argue that cultural identity is not antithetical to innovation. Music can show cultural identity through innovation, and at the same time inject new elements and ideas into Chinese culture. When ghostwriting about the nationality of Chinese music, music creators need to think deeply about the issues of cultural identity and cultural con-

flict. They can choose how to represent Chinese culture, while also staying alert to cultural challenges in a globalized environment. This requires musicians to have a keen understanding of the complexities of cultural identity, while also promoting cultural innovation and development.

(5) Controversy over music criticism and music creation

Music critics and music creators may disagree on the aesthetic standards of music. Critics sometimes evaluate music in terms of traditional and classic aesthetic standards, while creators may advocate new aesthetic perspectives that emphasize innovation and experimentation. The controversy involves critics' criticism of music creators, and whether creators should maintain creative freedom. Some musicians may believe that too much criticism and expectations will limit their creative freedom, while critics believe their role is to evaluate the quality of the music. Some music creators may pursue commercial success, while critics may advocate that the first priority of music is cultural expression^[8]. This controversy involves whether music should cater to the needs of the market or focus more on cultural communication and artistic expression. The controversy may also involve the emphasis and criticism on the national character of ghostwriting Chinese music. Some critics may argue that overemphasis on nationality leads to stereotyped and stale music, while creators may argue that it is an attempt to protect cultural traditions. Ghostwriting the nationality of Chinese music involves the expression of cultural identity, and critics and creators may disagree on how best to express Chinese cultural identity. Some may believe that ghostwriting nationality should be presented in a traditional way, while others may advocate expressing cultural identity through innovation. The controversy may involve the public influence of music criticism. Critics' reviews can influence the reception and marketing success of music, so the role of critics is widely discussed. Resolving the controversy over music criticism versus music creation requires constructive dialogue and mutual respect from all parties in the music industry. Critics and creators can work together to explore the role of music, aesthetic standards and cultural expressions to promote further development and innovation in the music field. Such controversies can also help push the music industry to think deeply and discuss different aspects of music.

(6) Audience demand and market pressure

Music creators usually consider the tastes and interests of the audience. Audience needs can influence the creative direction of music, as musicians may try to create music that suits the tastes of the audience in order to attract more listeners. Trends in the music market have an impact on music creation. Some musicians may be driven by market trends to create music related to market needs in order to be commercially successful. Audience demands and market pressures may sometimes conflict with the preservation of traditional culture and innovation. Musicians may feel pressure to find a balance between satisfying audience demands and preserving traditional culture. Music education plays an important role in shaping audience tastes and

needs. Music education can cultivate audiences' understanding and appreciation of different musical styles and forms, while also providing music creators with more creative inspiration. Music creators sometimes need to weigh the relationship between making their own music and catering to the needs of the market. Some musicians adhere to their desire to create, while others may be more inclined to pursue commercial success. The diversity of the music market provides opportunities for music creators to find an audience in different genres and styles of music. This diversity helps meet a variety of audience needs^[9]. When ghostwriting about the nationality of Chinese music, music creators need to carefully weigh audience needs and market pressure against the originality and cultural delivery of the music. Understanding audience needs can help musicians better interact with the audience, while also needing to keep the music innovative and artistic. This requires musicians to have a meticulous market insight while remaining passionate and loyal to the art of music.

7. Music education and preservation of traditions

Music education plays a key role in the preservation of traditions. Music education can impart knowledge, techniques and history of traditional music, helping new generations of musicians to understand and inherit the characteristics of traditional music. Music education needs to find a balance between tradition and innovation. It should not only teach traditional musical elements, but also encourage students to innovate on the basis of tradition to keep music alive. Music education can help pass on regional culture. The music and folk customs of different regions are unique, and music education can promote the inheritance and promotion of these regional cultures. Ghostwriting the nationality of Chinese music needs to consider the relationship between cultural protection and globalization. Music education can help Chinese music withstand the impact of globalization on traditional music, while also educating students to cope with the challenges of globalization. Music education should be diverse, including teaching different music genres and styles. This helps students gain a more comprehensive understanding of the diversity of Chinese music. In addition to formal music education, community participation and informal inheritance are also important ways to preserve traditional music. These approaches can help keep musical traditions alive, while complementing^[10] music education. Music education is closely related to the preservation of traditional music, and a balance needs to be struck between inheritance and development. While music education can provide a new generation of musicians with traditional music knowledge and skills, it should also encourage innovation and experimentation to ensure the vitality and inheritance of traditional music. This requires continued exploration of how best to combine music education with traditional preservation to support the development of Chinese music.

In summary:

Overall, the paper covers the key issues in the ghostwriting debate, reflecting the complex issues facing the Chinese music scene in the context of the cultural challenges of globalization and the protection of

national identity. Addressing these issues requires active participation and thoughtful approaches from all parties to advance the development and protection of Chinese music.

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